

A NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES BY FEM BASED ON DAMAGE MECHANICS

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SUMMARY: Woven fabric composites have been used in many fields such as cars and ships, etc. However, it is very difficult to evaluate the mechanical behavior of composites because of the complicated geometrical shape. In order to solve the difficulty, a finite element mesh generator based on the yarn data obtained from *WiseTex* software and the simulation technique of the mechanical behaviors of woven fabric composites have been developed. Especially, it is very difficult to estimate the damage development, because the complex damage modes like matrix cracks and delamination may occur at the crossover parts of the fiber bundle. We have developed a numerical simulation program which the complex damage modes in woven fabric composites can be estimated based on damage mechanics. The failure behaviors for woven fabric composites with hybrid bundles under static tensile load have been analyzed by the developed program. In this paper, the numerical results are described.

KEYWORDS: woven fabric composite, finite element modelling, damage development, hybrid bundles, damage mechanics

INTRODUCTION

Woven fabric reinforced plastics have been applied widely to many structures, because they have some advantages like easy handling, high lateral strength, etc. In addition, a woven architecture with spread tow has been developed to obtain superior properties. The architecture may produce the improvements of resin impregnation, high strength by small undulation. The mechanical behavior of woven fabric composites with spread tow has to be investigated. However, the estimation of damage development is very difficult, because matrix cracks and delamination at the crossover parts of fiber bundle may occur leading to complicated fracture modes in comparison with uni-directional fiber reinforced composites. If damages can be estimated with numerical simulation, it will become very useful tool for the estimation of mechanical properties of woven fabric composites. We have developed a numerical simulation program on damage development of woven fabric composites based on damage mechanics [1,2]. A tensile test and a fatigue test for a lamina of woven fabric composites with In-site observation had been carried out [3]. Though the effect of a disorder of pile-up for woven fabric composites laminate on damage development had been

investigated, the effect of a woven architecture with hybrid bundles on the damage development had not been considered in a previous paper [4].

We have developed a numerical simulation program on damage development of woven fabric composites with spread tow based on damage mechanics. The failure behaviors for woven fabric composites with several types of woven architectures and hybrid bundles under static tensile load have been analyzed by the developed program. In this paper, the numerical results of the damage states are described.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

Figure 1 shows the scheme of the structure analysis of woven fabric composites by the proposed numerical simulation method. The topology of a weave architecture is determined by the input data like a filament diameter, the architecture of strand, etc. The structural model of internal geometry of the fabrics is generated by *WiseTex* software [5]. FE model with yarns and matrix by the hexahedron element is generated by the developed numerical modeling program. The deformation and stress distribution can be evaluated by the generated mesh model and FEM software (SACOM).

Fig.1: Scheme of numerical procedure for mechanical behaviors of woven fabric composites

SIMULATION METHOD OF DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

In the simulation, the modeling of damage is very important. Woven fabric composites are treated as heterogeneous bodies with anisotropy for fiber bundles and with isotropy for matrix, respectively. The isotropic damage model is applied for matrix, and anisotropic damage model is applied for the fiber bundle, respectively. The damage in fiber bundle consists of four modes as shown in Fig.1 [1,2]. Mode *L* is dominated by fiber breaking, the others are matrix cracking caused by different stress components. The occurrence of damage can be predicted by Hoffman’s criterion. The damage mode is judged by the maximum value among the corresponding stress-to-strength ratios in Table 1. The constitutive equation can be obtained by the characterization of the damage mode.

Fig.1: Anisotropic damage mode

Table 1: Classification of damage mode

Maximum value	Damage mode
$\frac{s_L^2}{F_X^t F_X^c}$	Mode L
$\frac{s_T^2}{F_Y^t F_Y^c}$ or $\left(\frac{t_{LT}}{F_{TZ}^s}\right)^2$	Mode T & TL
$\frac{s_Z^2}{F_Z^t F_Z^c}$ or $\left(\frac{t_{ZL}}{F_{ZL}^s}\right)^2$	Mode Z & ZL
$\left(\frac{t_{TZ}}{F_{TZ}^s}\right)^2$	Mode TZ

(s, t : stress, F : strength
 t : tension, c : compression, s : shear)

NUNERICAL MODEL OF WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES

Hybrid bundles model composed of carbon and glass filaments

In our previous study [6], the effect of a spread tow on the damage development of woven fabric composites had been investigated. From the numerical and experimental results, the initial damages appeared in the centre-parts of a weft bundle. From the results of SEM observation about cross section of the fiber bundle, it is recognized that the volume fraction has the distribution in a fiber bundles. The center parts have higher volume fraction than the edge parts. We can guess that the high volume fraction area in a weft bundle induces the decrease of interfacial bonding force between a fiber and resin. In order to improve the mechanical properties, we showed the control of the volume fraction or the property in a fiber bundle. As an example, we have prepared numerical models of hybrid bundles composed of carbon and glass filaments. To estimate the effect of the woven architecture on the damage development, the finite element model of woven fabric composites with spread tow has been prepared as shown in Figs.2 and 3. Figure 2 shows the ‘hybrid bundles model’ composed of carbon filaments in centre parts and glass filaments in edge parts in a bundle. Figure 3 shows the finite element mesh model of woven fabric composites divided into 3D 8-node elements. The total number of nodes and elements are 13875, 11808, respectively. To make clear the damage, the only bundle parts are also indicated in Fig.3. We assumed that the two part (centre and edge) are same volume.

Fig.2: Typical example of woven fabric composites with hybrid bundles

Fig.3: Finite element model of woven FRP composed of hybrid bundles

NUNERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comparison of damage development of woven FRP composed of hybrid bundles

To estimate an effect of hybrid bundles on the damage development, four types of numerical models have been prepared. The composition of a bundle in each model is shown in Table 2. The symbol of 'g_c_' means the hybrid bundle model composed of glass fiber in centre parts of a bundle and carbon fiber in edge parts. To estimate the effect of volume fraction in centre parts, two models with volume fraction of 62.8% and 31.4% are also prepared as shown in 'g6c6' and 'g3c6', respectively. The bundle is treated as uni-directional fiber reinforced composites, and the mechanical properties can be calculated by the rule of mixture.

The damage development of woven fabric composites under on-axis tensile load has been analyzed by the developed computer program. Figure 4 shows the numerical results of stress-strain curves for several models. The hybrid models show the mechanical properties between the 'c6' and 'g6' models.

Figure 5 shows the damage states for models of 'g3c6' and 'c6'. In case of 'g3c6', the initial damage of transverse cracks (Mode T) appears at the edge of a weft bundle. However, no cracks occur at the centre-parts as shown in Fig.5(a-1). After that, the damages propagate and the Mode ZL, which is the damage mode caused by shearing stress at the warp bundles, appears at the strain 0.82% in Fig.5(b-1).

On the other hand, the numerical results for 'c6' model indicate that the initial damage appears at the centre and edge parts of a weft bundle as shown in Fig.5(a-2). The transverse cracks have developed widely in the edge parts of a weft bundle and the Mode ZL appears in the warp bundles at the strain 0.74%. From these results, it is revealed that the location of occurrence and propagation of damages are quite different due to the effect of hybrid bundles.

Table 2: Composition of a fiber bundle for numerical models

Type of numerical models	Centre-parts of a bundle	Edge-parts of a bundle
c6	CFRP (Vf = 62.8%)	
g6c6	GFRP (Vf = 62.8%)	CFRP (Vf = 62.8%)
g3c6	GFRP (Vf = 31.4%)	CFRP (Vf = 62.8%)
g6	GFRP (Vf = 62.8%)	

(Vf: Volume fraction of fiber)

Fig.4: Relation between stress and strain for several numerical models

An effect of composition of hybrid bundles in centre and edge parts

To estimate the effect of the arrangement of hybrid bundles on the mechanical behaviors, two numerical models are generated as shown in Table 3. The ‘g6c3’ model has a GFRP at the centre-parts of a bundle and a CFRP at the edge-parts. The ‘c3g6’ means the opposite of the composition of ‘g6c3’. As the comparison, a CFRP model ‘c3’ are also analyzed.

The numerical results of stress-strain curves under on-axis tensile load are shown in Fig.6. The effect of the Young’s modulus on the composition of hybrid bundles does not appear in the elastic region. However, the location of occurrence of initial damage is quite different due to the effect of the composition.

Figure 7 shows the damage states for models of ‘g6c3’ and ‘c3g6’. In case of the model of ‘g6c3’, the initial damages (Mode T) appears at the centre and edge parts in weft bundles in Fig.7(a-1), and the transverse cracks have developed widely in the weft one in Fig.7(b-1) at the strain 0.96%

On the other hand, in the case of the model of ‘c3g6’, the initial transverse cracks have appeared at the edge parts in weft bundles in Fig.7(a-2), and the cracks have developed mainly in weft bundles in Fig.7(b-2).

Furthermore, the strain levels when the initial damage and sequential damage appeared are shown in Fig.8. The strain levels for hybrid bundles are higher than that of traditional CFRP. The results indicate that the control of the composition and the volume fraction in the fiber bundles is effective to produce the high functional materials.

Table 3: Composition of a bundle for numerical models

Type of numerical models	Centre-parts of a bundle	Edge-parts of a bundle
c3	CFRP (Vf = 31.4%)	
g6c3	GFRP (Vf = 62.8%)	CFRP (Vf = 31.4%)
c3g6	CFRP (Vf = 31.4%)	GFRP (Vf = 62.8%)

(Vf: Volume fraction of fibers)

Fig.6: Relation between stress and strain for several numerical models

Fig.8: Strain levels when initial damage (Mode T) and sequential damage (Mode Z) appear

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Numerical procedure for mechanical behaviors of woven fabric composites has been described. FE models of bundles and matrix are generated by the hexahedron element, and the failure behaviors for woven fabric composites with several types of woven architectures and hybrid bundles under static tensile load have been analyzed by the developed computer program based on the damage mechanics. From the numerical results, the location of occurrence of damages is quite different due to the effect of a woven architecture. It is recognized that the damage development inside a bundle considering an effect of composition on mechanical behaviors which had been never observed in experiments can be predicted, and the strain of initial damage can be also evaluated conveniently by the proposed simulation.

We believe that the proposed numerical method is useful for the structural design, since the mechanical behaviors of woven fabric composites can be evaluated. And the control of the microstructure in bundles is effective to the produce of the high functional materials.

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